

Enhanced CO₂ methanation with ceramic 3D printed catalyst bed reactor

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ABSTRACT

3D printing is revolutionizing manufacturing, particularly in fields where complex shapes offer significant advantages, such as catalysis. This study demonstrates the potential of the ceramic-based additive manufacturing for producing catalytic beds for CO₂ methanation. In particular, it demonstrates the effectiveness of alumina catalytic beds with flat channels, fabricated via stereolithography, within the temperature range of 260 – 340 °C. 3D-printed beds show a 20 % performance increase compared to stainless-steel catalytic supports made through conventional milling and selective laser sintering. This research introduces a novel approach to produce catalytic materials, combining the advantages of additive manufacturing with the selection of materials that have optimal catalytic properties. Additionally, the 3D structuring of channels with a herringbone pattern further improves CO₂ conversion by 15 % at 300 °C, due to an increase of the functional area and enhanced flow distribution along the channel. Overall, this study paves the way for further advancements by incorporating advanced features into catalytic beds employing ceramic 3D printing technologies.

1. Introduction

During the last decades, research in sustainable energy storage solutions significantly increased, progressively enabling the transition towards renewable energies. In this regard, special attention has been drawn to the development of reactors for CO or CO₂ methanation as a prospective approach to produce valuable products for energy and chemical sectors. Deployment of CO₂ methanation solutions leads to the reduction of environmental pollution [1,2] by supporting carbon capture and utilization strategies [3] while providing an opportunity to achieve carbon neutrality of industry. Additionally, the methanation of carbon dioxide represents a solution to store the electricity produced by renewable sources in the form of synthetic methane [4], following the so-called Power-to-Gas route.

The thermochemical methanation, also known as Sabatier reaction (after *Sabatier* and *Senderens* proposed it in 1902 [5,6]), converts carbon oxides and hydrogen into methane, involving the following exothermic reactions [7]:

The process is typically performed at the temperature range of 150 – 600 °C. Although the methanation reaction is thermodynamically favorable ($\Delta G_{298\text{K}}: -130.8 \text{ kJ/mol}$) [8], the activity of a catalyst material is required to maintain high conversion rates and good selectivity. Most of the state-of-the-art catalysts include precious metals, such as Ir, Rh, Pt, Pd, which cost limits the full deployment of this technology [9–14]. Alternatively, elements as Ru, Ni, Fe and Co, offer a satisfactory balance between conversion rates and cost [15–17]. Among them, Ni represents a dominant catalyst, widely employed as the active phase due to its high activity, high availability and low cost [18,19]. To increase the exposure of the gases to the active material, these metals are usually dispersed on metal oxide supports, which improve the surface area, the dispersion and the attrition resistance of the particles. Thus, the performance of the catalyst is affected by the selection of the support material and its interaction with the active phase, metal loading, and fabrication method [20]. Materials such as alumina, ceria, zirconia and silica, have been proven to enhance and stabilize the performance of the catalyst [21–23]. Various studies showed the application of Al₂O₃, ZrO₂ or CeO₂ as the support for Ni catalyst, improving its activity and durability [24–29].

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Gac et al. [30] reported that the highest CO₂ conversion is achieved with a Ni/CeO₂ catalyst, while Ni reducibility decreases in order Ni/CeO₂ > Ni/ZrO₂ > Ni/Al₂O₃, which makes ceria-based Ni catalyst particularly favorable for CO₂ methanation.

The Sabatier reaction process could be performed using different configuration of the catalytic systems, which include fixed-bed [31,32], fluidized [33,34] and structured reactors [35,36]. Fixed bed reactors offer high reaction rate and possibility of steam recirculation; however, they require a cooling system to prevent hot spots formation. Fluidized systems need the use of a carrier medium to suspend the solid catalyst, resulting in high heating rates and complex thermal management, while exhibiting lower reaction rates and higher catalyst consumption due to the friction induced in the medium leading to catalyst attrition. Structured reactors combine the advantages of both reactor types, providing superior thermal control and enhanced heat transfer during the reaction process. These benefits have been particularly evident in microreactors [36–38], where the microscale nature of the systems leads to reduced catalyst degradation, lower energy consumption, and an increased surface-to-volume ratio. Thus, the micro-structuration of the reaction beds is considered as a prospective approach to enhance the performance of the fixed-bed systems by improving flow dynamics and heat distribution through the integration of micro-features. For instance, it was shown that the heat management in micro-channel reactors, created by stacking of etched stainless steel foils, was significantly improved compared to conventional systems, where maximum conversion peaks could be hidden by temperature gradients or heterogeneities [39,40]. Nonetheless, the upscaling and commercialization of the micro-channel devices for the methanation reaction especially remain constrained by the high overall cost of the reactors, which originates mostly from the relatively low reaction rate resulting in a large amount of catalyst required, which increases the reactor size considerably [35].

The state-of-the-art material selection for fabrication of reactor bed plates for CO₂ methanation is mainly oriented to stainless steel [40,41], aluminum [42], and corrosion-resistant alloys [43–45]. Metals generally offer high thermal conductivity and thermal diffusivity, enabling the fabrication of the mechanically resistant reactors with thin-wall micro-channels, which enhances thermal management in the reactor [46–48]. However, they present significant drawbacks compared to ceramic catalytic beds, including high thermal expansion coefficients, which could complicate catalyst deposition and reduce the adhesion of the active phase to the bed surface [49,50]. In contrast, ceramic materials exhibit excellent high-temperature and corrosion resistance, as well as strong compatibility with ceramic-supported catalysts, beneficial for the overall performance and stability of the catalytic device [51–53]. Nevertheless, their brittleness and complex manufacturing process hinder the widespread adoption of ceramic supports.

Typically, plates with micro-channels, subsequently assembled into fixed-bed reactors containing catalyst coatings, are manufactured through etching [54], milling [44,45,55] or hot pressing [42]. However, the field still demands innovative solutions to make the production process scalable, cost-effective, flexible, and customizable in terms of reactor design. In this regard, additive manufacturing (AM) represents a breakthrough in catalytic reactor fabrication due to its unique capacity to generate complex geometries on functional materials, while minimizing material waste, and optimizing both production time and cost [56]. The advantage of 3D printing technology is not laying on the realization of designs that could be obtained by other approaches, but the generation of designs that are not accessible by traditional manufacturing techniques without using subtractive methods, not desirable when employing advanced materials with a high added value. Several recent studies report the application of AM for manufacturing of catalytic beds and structured catalysts, as well as for rapid prototyping [57]. Some examples are provided by Danaci et al. [58,59] that show fabrication of porous structured stainless steel and copper supports for CO₂ methanation via robocasting. Similarly, Pérez et al. [60] developed a 3D printed multichannel reactor using selective laser melting (SLM) of

316L stainless steel. Moreover, Baena-Moreno et al. demonstrated the capabilities of the AM to produce micro-structured reactors for CO₂ methanation by fabricating structured catalysts with pseudo-gyroid geometries using SLM of the stainless steel powders [61,62]. Thus, current research is predominantly focused on the metal-based 3D printing of the catalytic materials and beds, while the full potential of the AM technologies, particularly in the context of ceramic-based devices, remains mainly unexplored [63].

In this work, alumina and stainless-steel support plates with micro-channels were produced via different 3D printing technologies (stereolithography and selective laser sintering, respectively) and with conventional manufacturing by subtractive machining. All the produced plates have been evaluated as reactor beds for CO₂ methanation using Ni/CeO₂ catalyst. Unique capabilities of ceramic 3D printing have been used to pattern alumina support plates, i.e. to generate a micro-structuration of the reaction channels. More specifically, the use of herringbone-shaped channels is proposed here proving the potential and uniqueness of 3D printing for creating a limitless range of novel designs. Overall, this work demonstrates the potential of ceramic-based 3D printing for further improvement of the conversion of carbon dioxide by design.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Fabrication of micro-channeled test plates

Two types of micro-channeled test plates were produced using alumina and stainless steel. Flat-channel bed plates consisting of an array of 16 channels with a width of 1 mm and a depth of 0.5 mm were fabricated in stainless steel and alumina (see the supplementary information section S1). This initial design was further enhanced by incorporating to the channel geometry of the alumina plates 200 µm-deep herringbone engravings, creating a 3D structured pattern. The herringbone design consists of an array of 1 mm-wide elements, inclined at 60° with respect to the edge of the channel. The selection of the design was performed targeting the maximization of the surface-to-volume ratio of the channel geometry, while preserving the manufacturing process stability. To ensure a valid comparison between the two types of samples, the same total gas channel volume was maintained across both configurations (see the supplementary information section S2).

Reference flat-channel test plates were produced by conventional subtractive machining of commercial stainless steel (AISI316) sheets. Additionally, AM technologies were used to fabricate equivalent flat-channeled stainless-steel plates and flat- and herringbone-channeled alumina plates. Stainless steel (AISI316) test plates were produced by Selective Laser Sintering (SLS), a layer-by-layer manufacturing technology, based on the partial sintering of a metal powder bed by a laser emission according to a computer-aided design (CAD). Each new thin layer of powder is distributed on the building platform with the leveling roller, while the building platform is going down after each sintering step to create the subsequent layers. Not-sintered powder and debris of the milling process are removed by immersion in ultrasonic bath with 10 % citric acid and consequently dried with compressed air.

Alumina test plates with both types of flat-channel and herringbone-like designs were manufactured via stereolithography (SLA) within a CERAMAKER C900 3D printer (3DCERAM, France). Commercial photocurable alumina paste (3DCERAM, France) with high ceramic loading is homogeneously spread on the building platform by a double doctor blade system to obtain the layer of 50 µm in thickness, which is subsequently solidified by UV-curing using a semiconductor laser (wavelength of 355 nm) in accordance with the CAD geometry. The process is performed slice by slice owing to the consistent motion of the building platform. As-printed alumina-based parts were removed from the printing platform, cleaned with a wax-based solution, and treated at high temperature to burn out the organic compounds and sinter the pieces (1550 °C, 2 h).

2.2. Catalyst preparation

Ni/CeO₂ has been chosen as catalyst for the present study due to the already known high conversion efficiency towards the CO₂ methanation [64]. The ceria is used as a support to improve the dispersion of the active phase while ensuring the compatibility of the active phase, i.e. Ni particles. The catalyst material was prepared by impregnation of nickel onto ceria, which was performed using Ni(NO₃)₂·6H₂O (Fisher Scientific, USA) and CeO₂ powder (Sigma Aldrich, USA) mixed to obtain 20 wt % of metallic Ni in the final composition. The mixture was calcined at 450 °C for 6 h to complete the process.

The catalyst layer was deposited within micro-channels by wash coating of Ni/CeO₂-based suspension. For this purpose, polyvinylalcohol (PVA, Mowiol 40–88, Sigma Aldrich, USA) as a binder was dissolved in deionized water under stirring at 65 °C for 3 h. Then, 10 wt% of catalyst and 1 wt% of acetic acid were added to the solution and stirred again at 65 °C for 3 h. Stirring was then continued at room temperature for 2 to 3 days until homogeneous solution was obtained. The final ratio of the components of the suspension was binder:water:catalyst:acetic acid = 5:84:10:1.

The microchannels were filled with the as-prepared suspension, while the excess of the material was removed by means of a sharp blade. After the deposition, the samples were dried for 1 h and fired at 450 °C for 6 h to attach the catalyst to the substrate. The procedure was repeated to obtain total amount of about 40 mg of catalyst for each plate [65].

2.3. Materials characterization

In order to ensure the presence of the desired active phases, XRD was performed on the obtained active phase and supports. The XRD analysis of the catalyst powder was carried out using Bruker-D8 Advance using copper K α radiation (1.5418 Å) with a nickel filter and Lynxeye 1D detector in a range of 2 θ from 20° to 80°, imposing sample rotation. The microstructure of the supports and the catalyst layer fabricated in this study was analyzed via scanning electron microscopy (SEM) using Leo 1550 VP microscope with a Gemini column (Zeiss, Germany) provided with a hot-cathode emission with LaB₆-crystal. Confocal optical profilometry (PLu Neox, Sensofar, Spain) was used to obtain the topographic characterization of the 3D printed part surfaces, ensuring the reliable patterning of the designed geometries. The roughness measurements were performed via mobile instrument MarSurf PS10 (Mahr GmbH, Germany).

To evaluate the adhesion of the catalyst to the substrate plates, a vibration test was performed, reproducing conditions, which are similar

to the real operational environment. For this purpose, the plates covered with a layer of active catalyst material were placed in the setup with the specific acceleration (2.5 G) imposed by an electrically controlled piston. The catalyst loss from the surface of the substrate was calculated by the comparison of the initial and final (after 5 min.) weights of the samples.

2.4. Catalytic activity evaluation

Different fabricated test plates (SS316L and Al₂O₃) covered with the catalyst layer were used in a standard face-to-face configuration to obtain a micro-channel-like reactor. Stacks of four plates are placed in stainless steel housing (Fig. 1a) designed to ensure the gas tightness of the system. This is a re-usable housing based on previous tests published by Knitter et Liauw [66]. The plates were fixed inside the housing with two triangular notches integrated to their geometry, which allowed to ensure the appropriate position and the alignment of the catalytic bed in the measuring setup (Fig. 1b). A lid is placed and welded on top of the housing, which ensures gas tightness and sufficient resistance to operate under pressure of 6 bars. The housing was placed on a heating platform enabling the operation of the system at 260 – 340 °C.

Prior to the experiment, the catalyst material was reduced under 20 mL min⁻¹ of hydrogen at 500 °C for 2 h. The reactors were operated at the pressure of 6 bar, while a mixture of carbon dioxide and hydrogen was supplied to the set-up in a ratio 1:4, maintaining a Weight Hourly Space Velocity (WHSV) of 45 L/h·g_{cat} for all the experiments (see the supplementary information section S3). A minor fixed flow of nitrogen was employed for the calibration of the gas chromatograph. A stability test was performed during 50 h of continuous operation of the test-plate reactor at 290 °C.

Gas composition during the reaction was analyzed with the Agilent 7890A (Agilent, USA) multidimensional process chromatograph with two thermal conductivity detectors and one flame ionization detector. The method acquisition, the quantitative and qualitative analysis were supported by the Agilent OpenLAB CDS ChemStation Workstation software M8301AA.

The CO₂ conversion is calculated based on the following equation (3):

$$X_{CO_2} = \frac{nCO_{2,in} - nCO_{2,out}}{nCO_{2,in}} \times 100 \quad (3)$$

The conversion rate was evaluated over the entire temperatures range, while each value was averaged over at least three measurements.

Fig. 1. Stainless steel housing for the fabricated test plates: (a) Scheme. The welding of the lid can be opened after the test to examine the substrates. (b) The image of the housing base where the alignment notches are highlighted.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Characterization of the fabricated catalytic bed

Flat-channel stainless steel and alumina test plates were produced using 3 different manufacturing techniques: mechanical machining of the sheets, SLS and SLA. The influence of the manufacturing technique selection on the surface finish and resolution of the channels, which are affecting the attachment of the catalyst to the substrate, is analyzed by SEM and reported in Fig. 2. The plates produced by mechanical milling of stainless-steel sheets present sharp edges and flat uniform surfaces, showing typical features of the applied manufacturing technique (Figs. 2a and 2b). In case of powder-based AM technology, SLS, the

Fig. 2. Top-view SEM pictures of a single flat micro-channel produced by different techniques and material with the detailed view provided on the right: (a)-(b) Milled 316L; (e)-(f) SLS 3D printed 316L; (i)-(j) SLA 3D printed alumina. Microstructure of the catalyst layer on top of the different types of support plates with the detailed view provided on the right: (c)-(d) Milled 316L; (g)-(h) SLS 3D printed 316L; (k)-(l) SLA 3D printed alumina.

quality of the surface is constrained by the dimension of the metal particles. Thus, the production of the catalytic supports by SLS leads to the rough surface of the test plates covered by the partially sintered residual powder (Figs. 2e and 2f). In contrast, alumina test plates produced by SLA demonstrate defined and clear flat microchannels (Fig. 2i), where one could notice sintering domains with a diameter less than 10 μm (Fig. 2j), which is smaller than the dimension of the residual metal particles observed for the stainless-steel plates produced by SLS.

The surface finishing of the different samples has been evaluated by carrying out roughness measurements reported in Table 1. Typically, the support surface roughness is correlated with the catalyst attachment quality, foreseeing a higher adhesion on surfaces characterized by higher roughness [58,67]. The milled steel surface exhibits the lowest value of roughness (R_a of 0.14 μm), which is consistent with the SEM images of the surface, while the SLS printed supports are characterized by the highest roughness of 7.98 μm and irregularities up to 44.22 μm . At the same time, alumina test plates demonstrate intermediate roughness values (R_a of 1.38 μm), which is sufficient to provide adequate catalyst attachment and offer high surface area to facilitate the available sites for the catalyst particles.

The microstructure of the catalyst layer deposited on the SS316L and alumina flat-channel support plates was evaluated. On the milled stainless-steel surface, the formation of cracks (with the size of $\sim 100 \mu\text{m}$) and delamination of the material occurred, in particular, close to the edges of the microchannel (Fig. 2c). For the SS316L plates produced by SLS, the generation of similar defects could not be clearly noticed in the same zone as for the milled supports, because some of the cracks could be hidden by the rough structure of the top catalyst layer (Fig. 2g). Both types of stainless-steel plates show the appearance of sub-micron cracks located in the middle part of the channels (Figs. 2d and 2h, respectively). At the same time, SLA 3D printed alumina plates demonstrate a homogeneous layer of the catalyst well-attached to the surface of the microchannels (Figs. 2k and 2l). The sponge-like microstructure of the layer is beneficial for facilitating the gas diffusion at the catalyst surface. In addition to the surface roughness, one of the potential factors affecting the catalyst microstructure could be associated with the different thermomechanical behaviors of the support materials and the active phase, leading to a defect formation during the thermal treatment performed to attach the catalyst layer. The TEC (Thermal Expansion Coefficient) mismatch is higher in the case of the stainless-steel substrates compared to the alumina plates, which could promote the crack generation within the catalyst layer ($\text{TEC}_{\text{alumina}}$ is $\sim 6.7 \times 10^{-6} \text{K}^{-1}$ [68], $\text{TEC}_{\text{stainless steel}} \sim 19.5 \times 10^{-6} \text{K}^{-1}$ [69], $\text{TEC}_{\text{ceria}} \sim 10.6 \times 10^{-6} \text{K}^{-1}$ [70]). Thus, catalytic supports produced from alumina using SLA 3D printing represent an optimal solution in terms of achieving the required catalyst microstructure, chemical compatibility and sufficient surface roughness of the substrate. However, there are also measures available to improve the adhesion of alumina or ceria on stainless steel or nickel-based alloys, which are not the subject of the current paper.

Weight loss of the catalyst determined by the vibration test is reported in Table 2 as a function of the plate material and manufacturing technique. The weakest adhesion is observed for milled SS316L supports (the loss of $\sim 2.43 \text{wt}\%$), which could be ascribed to the lowest surface roughness of the plates and high TEC mismatch between the support material and active phase. An increase of the surface roughness obtained by SLS 3D printing of the test plates leads to a decrease of the catalyst loss to 1.39 wt%. SLA 3D printed alumina substrates represent the

Table 1
Roughness values of the flat-channel support plates.

Manufacturing process/material	R_a , μm	R_q , μm	R_z , μm
Milling/316L stainless steel	0.14	0.17	0.70
SLS/316L stainless steel	7.98	9.91	44.22
SLA/ Al_2O_3	1.38	1.94	8.70

Table 2
Catalyst loss for the different test plates after the vibration test.

Manufacturing process/material	wt.% catalyst loss
Milling/ 316L	2.43
SLS/316L	1.39
SLA/Alumina	1.06

sufficient attachment of the catalyst with a weight loss of ~ 1.06 wt%. Therefore, the layers deposited on the stainless-steel support plates, both milled and SLS 3D printed, are characterized by higher weight loss values than the ones distributed on the alumina substrates, which is coherent with the SEM analysis of catalyst plates microstructure. This effect is related to the combination of factors, such as thermal and chemical compatibility between two oxides, which positive effect is reported to improve the catalyst attachment to the support structure [71,72]. Note that to ensure compatibility, both stainless-steel and alumina test plates were coated with the same catalyst ink composition, which was initially optimized for application on metallic substrates [65,73]. In this regard, one potential strategy to further reduce catalyst loss from the 3D printed alumina test plates is to optimize the ink formulation and deposition specifically for ceramic bed coating. Alternatively, enhancing catalyst adhesion could be achieved by increasing surface roughness, for example, through spray coating the 3D printed alumina substrate with Al_2O_3 powder. In general, the weight loss of the catalyst material does not exceed 2.5 wt% for all the catalytic plates, which is sufficient for the effective operation in CO_2 methanation reaction, since a significant decrease of the catalytic performance has been reported for systems suffering from catalyst losses as high as 10–12 wt% [58,74]. This is, however, also largely affected by the (over)dimensioning of the reactor and the local distribution of such losses.

The unique capabilities of the AM to define advanced features of the catalytic beds are further explored by SLA 3D printing of alumina catalytic plates with micro-channels 3D-structured with the herringbone pattern (Figs. 3d and 3e), which were compared with the initial flat-channel design (Figs. 3a and 3b). The topography mapping is used to confirm the precise reproduction of the integrated microfeatures (Figs. 3c and 3f), while maintaining the desirable surface quality of the 3D printed ceramic support. Thus, the incorporation of herringbone engrave to the micro-channels of the catalytic reactors extends the functional area, available for the deposition of the active phase, for 25 %, which leads to an increase of the active sites involved in the CO_2 methanation reaction.

It should be mentioned that alumina SLA 3D printed test plates show thermal conductivity values coherent with the ones of conventionally manufactured alumina (see supplementary information section S4), which highlights the high quality of the here produced functional

ceramics.

3.2. Catalyst characterization

The crystal structures of the phases present on the catalytic device are investigated over the different production and operation stages (as-produced, calcined and reduced catalyst after the methanation test) depending on the nature of the produced microchannel reactor beds. Fig. 4 shows the XRD spectra of the catalyst material on the milled stainless-steel plates (Fig. 4a), SLS 3D printed stainless steel plates (Fig. 4b), and SLA 3D printed alumina plates (Fig. 4c).

The as-produced catalyst powder shows the characteristic peaks of CeO_2 (ICDD-01-081-0792) and NiO (ICDD-00-078-0429), which evolves to a metal nickel peak (ICDD-00-001-1258) after the reduction process. In the case of the milled stainless-steel plates, after the deposition and calcination at 450°C , the presence of ceria and nickel oxide peaks is observed accompanied by the appearance of some secondary phases. Traces of iron (ICDD-00-040-1139) and chromium oxides (ICDD-00-032-0285) from the substrate are detected at low angles (25.5° , 26.7° , 31° , 32°), while the formation of CeFeO_3 (at $\sim 57.5^\circ$) (ICDD-00-022-0166) can be identified. The dimension of the peak indicates a minor presence of CeFeO_3 , while it is not detected after the reduction.

Regarding the catalyst deposited and characterized on SLS-produced plates, a FeNi alloy (ICDD-00-047-1405) is formed after the calcination of the catalyst (peak at 50.8° , enlargement of peak at 43.5°). The formation of the cerium ferrite is not clearly observed; however, it could be presumably present in small amounts. In the case of the alumina SLA 3D printed plates, the XRD spectra show no interaction between the catalyst and the substrate.

At the same time, nickel metal reduction is confirmed, while no degradation of the support or catalyst materials is observed at the XRD spectra obtained after testing in operation conditions for methanation reaction.

3.3. Catalytic performance evaluation of flat-channeled plates

The functionality of the flat-channeled test plates produced with different materials and manufacturing techniques was proved by testing the catalyst coatings under conditions of CO_2 methanation at different temperatures (calculated employing Eq. (1)). In all cases, the conversion of CO_2 presents a characteristic sigmoid shape as shown in Fig. 5. In the lower temperature range, the conversion values vary between 10 and 20 %, while complete conversion is reached only at $T > 330^\circ\text{C}$ for alumina-based plates (as reported in previous works for the same reaction [75]).

Stainless-steel plates fabricated with SLS demonstrate a better performance than milled SS316L supports with an improvement of 7 % in the conversion at 300°C . That is likely related to the increased surface

Fig. 3. SLA 3D printed alumina test plates: (a) with flat channels, general view; (b) with flat channels, detailed view; (c) with flat channels, surface topography; (d) with herringbone engrave, general view; (e) with herringbone engrave, detailed view; (f) with herringbone engrave, surface topography.

Fig. 4. XRD spectra of the catalyst as produced in powder form, as deposited and calcined over the plates, and after running the methanation test on the (a) milled SS316L support; (b) SLS 3D printed stainless steel support; (c) SLA 3D printed alumina support.

roughness of the substrate fabricated via SLS, which leads to an increase of the catalyst active area. Moreover, it was previously demonstrated that manufacturing via SLS partially reduces the catalyst loss during operation, which could also be partially responsible of the observed performance enhancement of the catalyst substrate. On the other hand, the alumina SLA 3D printed plates present a notable improvement

Fig. 5. CO₂ conversion as a function of temperature for different test-plates material and manufacturing techniques.

compared to SS316L substrates with 20 % increase of the CO₂ conversion at 300 °C. Moreover, full conversion is reached at a remarkable lower temperature. The origin of this enhancement is likely related to the higher compatibility between the active phase of the catalyst and the alumina of the plates, often used as a support for the Ni active particles [35,58]. On one hand, this compatibility could be related to stronger interaction between Ni-based catalyst and alumina substrates compared to various types of the support materials [7,76,77]. On the other hand, the use of alumina reduces the TEC mismatch between the active phase and the material of the catalytic bed compared to stainless steel; thus, improving the catalyst adhesion and enhancing the conversion efficiency. In contrast, the application of the stainless steel beds could result in the migration of Fe or Cr from the substrate to the active phase [78], decreasing the reactor performance, while this is not present in case of alumina test plates.

A stability test for 50 h was carried out at 290 °C for the best performing test plates, i.e. stainless-steel SLS and alumina SLA 3D-printed catalytic plates (Fig. 6). Beyond the difference in the conversion rate, both conversion curves are characterized by an initial conditioning period of about 10 h, which generates the strongest degradation, for a further stabilization during the rest of the operation, where the reactors

Fig. 6. Degradation over time of the CO₂ conversion using SLA printed alumina plates and SLS printed stainless steel plates.

with flat channels fabricated with SLS in stainless steel and with SLA in alumina present a degradation rate of 0.23 %/h and 0.13 %/h, respectively, indicating a noticeably better stability of the performance of the plates fabricated in alumina.

3.4. Catalytic performance evaluation of plates with herringbone-like channels

After validation of SLA 3D-printed alumina as a highly performing material for supporting CO₂ methanation, the catalytic performance of test plates with enhanced geometry (herringbone-like channels) was studied. For this purpose, the catalytic activity of the system with the herringbone pattern engraved is compared to the flat-channel reactor design fabricated in the same material. According to conversion rates presented in Fig. 7, the fabrication of highly complex channels results in an overall improvement of the performance of CO₂ conversion, reaching 15 % at 300 °C, which could be attributed to the associated increase of the functional area of ~ 25 %. At the same time, the 3D structuration of the channels is likely involving a redistribution of the species flows during the reaction, increasing the mass transfer of the reactive gases [79,80].

Overall, it is demonstrated that the use of SLA 3D printing provides a novel perspective strategy for the fabrication of catalyst coated carrier structures for the CO₂ methanation reaction. Moreover, it is shown that the addition of advanced geometries to the configuration of the catalytic support channel allows the enhancement of the conversion due to the direct increase of the reaction area, which could not be straightforwardly reached with the use of conventional ceramic manufacturing techniques.

4. Conclusions

Catalyst support plates with microchannels were fabricated from stainless steel and alumina using SLS and SLA 3D printing technologies. All types of plates were employed as reactor carriers for the CO₂ methanation reaction with Ni/CeO₂ catalyst coatings. The catalytic performance of the systems was compared with the reference reactor configuration produced through conventional machining of stainless-steel sheets. A 7 % improvement in CO₂ conversion was achieved for the SLS 3D printed stainless steel plates attributed to the surface modification. Furthermore, the functionality of SLA 3D printed alumina plates as a catalytic bed for CO₂ methanation reaction was demonstrated, reaching the improvement of 20 % compared to stainless steel carrier plates. Finally, a 3D structuration of the channels employing a herringbone-like pattern showed an additional enhancement of the performance of 15 %. Overall, this work proves a clear route towards improving performance in catalysis by design employing additive manufacturing of metals and, especially, ceramics such as alumina.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

N. Kostretsova: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Investigation, Formal analysis. **A. Pesce:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **C. Hofmann:** Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **S. Neuberger:** Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **I. Babeli:** Investigation. **M. Nuñez:** Methodology, Investigation. **A. Morata:** Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **G. Kolb:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Conceptualization. **M. Torrell:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **A. Tarancón:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial

Fig. 7. CO₂ conversion for different test plate designs produced in alumina by SLA as a function of temperature.

interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2025.161752>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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